

SHERD SHEET

MATCH WITH OTHER CORPORA

CORPUS	WARE DESIGNATION	TYPE DESIGNATION
	<i>Red Ware</i>	

I. TECHNIQUE

A. HAND MADE	1. Hand Modelled	2. Coiling	3. Plate Building
	4. Core Moulding	5. Turntable (up. pt.)	6. Other
B. TURNTABLE	?	C. WHEELMADE	?
E. CASTING			

II. FABRIC

A. TEXTURE OF CLAY			
GENERAL:	Coarse	Medium X	Fine
1. Pebble	2. Granule	3. Very Coarse	4. Coarse
5. Medium	6. Fine	7. Very Fine	8. Silt
B. COMPOSITION Type of Clay: <i>Nile Alluvial</i>			
TEMPER (General): Heavy Medium X Light			
1. Material	<i>Sand</i>	<i>chaff - few</i>	
2. Particle Size	<i>Med.</i>	<i>fine</i>	
C. FRACTURE COLOR			General Description
			<i>THICK DARK Grey to Red RBr at walls</i>
D. HARDNESS		E. POROSITY	
<i>HARD</i>			
F. TRANSVERSE STRENGTH		G. PERMEABILITY	

III. SURFACE PROPERTIES

A. SURFACE TREATMENT			
1. Untreated	2. Wheel Finish	?	a. ribbing
			b. scrapped or shaved
3. Hand Finish	a. smoothed	X	b. polished by burnishing
	d. scrapped		e. scratched or combed
			c. polished by rubbing
			f. other
4. Coating	a. wash	b. slip	c. glaze
	<i>RED WASH</i>		
B. SURFACE TEXTURE <i>SMOOTH</i>			
C. MECHANICAL CONDITION OF SURFACE <i>Scratch or comb horizontal incised lines toward lower part. Fine dulled (shallow) horizontal striations to top. INSIDE: Pronounced undulations, rib-like w/ very fine horizontal</i>			
D. LUSTER	1. Matte	X	2. Low
			3. Medium
			4. High
E. SURFACE COLOR		General Description	CEC. Munsell
		<i>Red - Red Brown</i>	<i>F11</i>

IV. DECORATION

A. TECHNIQUE			
1. Incised	2. Impressed	3. Gouged	4. Pinched
5. Modelled	6. Moulded	7. Painted	8. Inlaid

REPORT ON THE

EXCAVATIONS AT

striations over whole interior wall.